

1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Code	Inclusion criteria	Code	Exclusion criteria
IC1	Studies whose thematic focus is the generation, detection, or automatic repair of code comments.	EC1	Gray literature, duplicate studies, or works without peer review.
IC2	Research published in English.	EC2	If multiple publications from the same project exist, only the most complete version with the greatest contribution is retained.
IC3	Studies published in indexed journals, scientific conferences, or proceedings subjected to peer review.	EC3	Studies that do not address the characteristics of interest for the review, such as <i>comment smells</i> , causes, tools, metrics, or associated processes.
IC4	Recent studies (2019–2026) whose information reflects the current state of the field.	EC4	Works with a superficial approach to the topic or without sufficient analytical depth.
IC5	Studies with a clear, sequential methodology supported by comprehensible arguments.	EC5	Articles without publicly available access or with restrictions that prevent review of their full content.
		EC6	Studies focused exclusively on <i>Code Review Comments</i> , <i>pull request</i> comments, or review communication not integrated as persistent code documentation.

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria applied during title and abstract screening.